
A Comparative Analysis of Educational Curriculum Systems in Indonesia and China: Perspectives on Structure, Content, and Pedagogical Approaches

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ABSTRACT: China is famous for its very high-quality education; it has a very detailed and structured education system, from primary to university. China also has a culture that values education, so its people care and try hard to improve the quality of education. This research aims to compare curriculum systems in Indonesia and China. This research method is a literature review carried out by collecting relevant sources and using a descriptive analysis approach. The results of this research are: 1) Both Indonesia and China have carried out curriculum reforms to follow society's needs. 2) Indonesia has a 12-year compulsory education program, while China has nine years. 3) Despite their differences, national education goals in both countries are the same: to develop balanced, qualified, and characterized individuals to contribute to national development. 4) The government determines the content/material taught in both countries at the elementary-middle school level. However, China does not have mandatory subjects at the high school level, while the government still determines Indonesia. 5) Learning strategies in Indonesia include group, project, and inquiry-based learning; China has unique strategies, such as implementing naps during learning. 6) National exams are no longer implemented in Indonesia, while there is still a national exam known as the Gaokao Exam in China.

KEYWORDS: Curriculum, China, Indonesia, Education

INTRODUCTION

The education system is fundamental in developing a country's human resources (HR). Individuals have the knowledge, skills, and character to contribute to the nation's progress through education. Each country has its own education system policy, including Indonesia and China.

Indonesia and China are two Asian countries with large populations and unique education systems. Indonesia, the country with the most significant Muslim majority in the world, adheres to an education system whose basis is Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. Meanwhile, China, the communist country with the largest population in the world, implements an education system oriented towards national development and mastery of science.

One of the world's best education systems is in China, which produces intelligent, disciplined and competitive graduates. Its students rank at the top in reading ability compared to other countries. This is not surprising because the literacy rate in China will reach 99.4% in 2023. (Sassi, 2024, p. 336) Meanwhile, in Indonesia, the literacy competency level of elementary to high school students is still relatively moderate, with an average of not reaching 60%. This shows that there is still a reasonably large gap between the Indonesian and Chinese / Chinese education systems. (2023a)

These differences certainly have an impact on the curriculum structure implemented. The educational curriculum bridges educational goals and learning practices in schools. The education and learning process cannot be separated from the curriculum. The curriculum acts like a map that guides all educational activities in school. It also benefits parents, communities, teachers, supervisors, and students. Teachers must have a strong understanding of the curriculum to plan, implement, and assess instruction effectively. Studying the comparison of educational curricula in these two countries can provide valuable insight.

Research on the comparison of educational curriculum systems between Indonesia and China has also been carried out by previous researchers, namely research conducted by Zai et al. with the title "Comparison of the Dynamics of Development of the Chinese and Indonesian Civics Curriculum", which concluded that both the educational curriculum in Indonesia and in China are the same. And also undergo dynamic adjustments. This is done to keep up with current developments and the current situation in each country. In other words, they both strive to improve the quality of education by adapting to society's needs. (Zai et al., 2023) There is also research conducted by Muslim et al. in their journal entitled "Analysis of Education Policy in Japan, Finland, China and Indonesia in Supporting Sustainable Development Goals", which concluded that all four countries are equally committed to advancing education. Because the author focuses on discussing China and Indonesia, the journal Muslim et al. concludes that China focuses on developing superior and characterful human resources through education. At the same time, Indonesia seeks to improve

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the accessibility and quality of education as a whole, including improving the quality of teachers, educational facilities, and services and cultivating national character. These differences reflect the priorities of each country in building a quality next generation. (Muslim et al., 2021)

These two studies are different from the author's research because Zai et al.'s research only focused on comparing the Civics curriculum but did not discuss the comparison of the curriculum as a whole. Muslim et al.'s research focuses on education policy in four countries, namely Japan, Finland, China and Indonesia in general. In contrast, the author's research focuses only on education in China and Indonesia.

The author compares education curriculum systems in Indonesia and China through this research. The research will focus on the curriculum structure, namely objectives, content/material, strategies and the assessment (evaluation) system used. By understanding the comparison of curriculum systems in the two countries, we can formulate strategies so that the quality of education in Indonesia improves and is more relevant to current developments and the needs of global society.

METHOD

This qualitative research uses a descriptive-analytical approach to deeply understand and interpret the phenomenon of comparing the Indonesian and Chinese education curriculum systems. The method used in this research is a literature review, namely a method of collecting data by reviewing various literature such as books, internet articles, and journals related to the topic discussed, (Rusmawan, 2019, p. 104) In this case, it is about comparing the Indonesian and Chinese education curriculum systems. Data was collected by sorting reference sources and scientific literature, then reviewed, analyzed and presented systematically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Education Curriculum in Indonesia

The term curriculum has two meanings: a narrow and broad understanding. In the narrow sense, the term curriculum refers to several subjects (Curriculum as the sum of planned content) that students must study to obtain a diploma. Meanwhile, in a broad sense, the curriculum is not only limited to subjects, but more than that, the curriculum contains all learning experiences (Curriculum as the learning experience) provided by the school to impact students' personal development positively. These opportunities include various in-depth student activity plans in the form of teaching materials, recommendations for teaching and learning techniques, and program arrangements that allow them to be implemented in line with educational goals (2023b, p. 1).

Curriculum development in Indonesia must pay attention to Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution, which outline the nation's outlook on life. The curriculum is dynamic, which means it is always adapted to the demands of society, advances in science and technology, students' IQ levels, cultural norms and value systems. Since 1945, Indonesia has changed its national education curriculum several times, namely in 1947, 1952, 1964, 1968, 1975, 1984, 1994, 1999, 2004, 2006, 2013, and most recently in 2022. A brief explanation of each -Each curriculum is explained as follows:

First, the 1947 Curriculum, known as the "leer plan" (lesson plan), was the first curriculum developed in Indonesia after independence. Created two years after the proclamation, this curriculum is an essential historical milestone in Indonesia's educational journey. This curriculum was developed by a working group tasked with developing educational concepts. Developing individual Indonesian people who are autonomous, sovereign, and equal to other countries is the primary priority in the 1947 curriculum. This curriculum emphasises character education, love of the country, and community education rather than the mind. The 1947 curriculum only continued previous practices because Dutch and Japanese colonial educational institutions still influenced it. (Iramadan, 2019)

Second, the 1952 Curriculum, also known as the 1952 Decomposed Lesson Plan, refined the 1947 Curriculum. Created five years after independence, this curriculum was essential in building a more stable and structured national education system. This curriculum has been directed at a national education system. The main characteristic of the 1952 Curriculum is that each lesson plan relates the material to real-world situations. According to the subject syllabus, A teacher can only teach one topic at a time. (Raharjo, 2020).

Third, the 1964 Curriculum, or the 1964 Education Plan, is the curriculum implemented in Indonesia under the government of President Soekarno. The birth of this curriculum was driven by the government's desire to strengthen moral education and noble character based on Pancasila, as well as to form the next generation who adhere to the Pancasila ideology. The government's emphasis on providing academic information to individuals at the elementary school level through the "Pancawardhana" program, which includes moral, intellectual, emotional/artistic growth, keprigelan (skills), and physical development, is a characteristic of this curriculum (Febriyenti et al., 2023).

Fourth, the first curriculum in the New Order era was the 1968 curriculum. This was created to replace the 1964 Education Plan curriculum, which was seen as the result of the Old Order, and was aimed at making actual Pancasila people who were tough, physically healthy, educated, skilled, moral, ethical, and devout. This curriculum represents a shift towards pure implementation of the 1945 Constitution. The 1968 curriculum is different from the previous curriculum in several ways; the material taught is still

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theoretical and not much related to practical issues in the field, and the primary focus lies on what kind of learning is suitable to be given to students at all levels of education, education focuses on the development of a solid and healthy body and to increase intelligence and skills (I Wayan Kandia, 2023, p. 68).

Fifth, the 1975 Curriculum was designed to consider the effective and efficient achievement of learning goals. This curriculum defines the term lesson unit or lesson plan about each subject, which is then developed with broad guidelines, targeted learning objectives, materials, tools, teaching and learning activities, and evaluation. However, the 1975 Curriculum was widely criticized because it burdened teachers with excessive administrative tasks in compiling these details (Hidayat et al., 2023, p. 40).

Sixth, the 1984 Curriculum (CBSA), also known as the 1975 enhanced curriculum, is an educational curriculum published in 1984 in Indonesia. This curriculum carries a process skills approach, where students become subjects in learning. CBSA uses an Active Student Learning Approach (CBSA), where students observe, group, discuss and report the results of these observations. This curriculum leads to an educational orientation oriented towards instructional goals and uses a process approach that emphasizes mental, intellectual and emotional activity. The 1984 curriculum is oriented towards instructional goals and uses varied approaches and methods to achieve individual student competencies (Wardhana, 2021, p. 20).

Seventh, the 1994 Curriculum and the 1999 curriculum supplement are an attempt to integrate the previous curriculum, namely the 1975 and 1984 curricula. However, efforts to combine objectives and learning processes have not produced results. This has received a lot of criticism from the public, who think that the learning load borne by students is too heavy. Local content material, which includes regional arts, language and skills, adapts to the needs of each region. Community organizations are also asked to include specific topics in the curriculum. Finally, the 1994 Curriculum became a very dense curriculum. 1998, the Soeharto regime stepped down, and the 1999 Curriculum Supplement appeared. However, the changes were more about just patching in some lesson materials (n.d., p. 54).

Eighth, the 1994 curriculum was replaced with the Competency Based Curriculum (KBK) in 2004. This curriculum emphasizes achieving individual and classical student competency, focuses on learning outcomes, and recognizes diversity. This curriculum uses a variety of strategies and techniques, and in addition to teachers, additional learning resources that meet educational requirements also serve as learning resources. KBK also covers relevant pedagogical principles and essential concepts regarding teaching and achieving specified competencies in learning. Clear competency criteria are another characteristic of this curriculum that will facilitate the development of educational institution evaluation systems (Sugianto, 2022, p. 353).

Ninth, the 2006 curriculum is known as the Education Unit Level Curriculum (KTSP). This curriculum emphasizes flexibility in curriculum design at the school level, allowing each educational institution to adapt objectives, content, learning methods and assessments according to local needs and student characteristics. This concept is seen as a step towards increasing education's relevance to real life, enabling a student-centred learning approach, and integrating character education in every aspect of learning. Therefore, KTSP represents an effort to align education with the needs of society and the world of work and promote holistic personal development for students (Solihatul Wahidah, 2016, p. 3).

Tenth, curriculum 2013 or K-13. Emphasizes competency thinking based on attitudes, skills and knowledge. As a facilitator, the teacher supports observation, questioning, reasoning, and communicating with students about what they have learned after completing the program. Students themselves are then required to have critical thinking skills, interpersonal and interpersonal skills, as well as responsibility for the environment (Aisyah & Astuti, 2021).

The most recent is the independent curriculum (Merdeka Curriculum), which was just launched in 2022; the Merdeka Curriculum, or Prototype Curriculum, is a curriculum that prioritizes student competency, character development and flexibility while still emphasizing core subjects. This curriculum allows educators, students and educational institutions to implement more interactive and collaborative learning activities. Merdeka Curriculum also provides many teaching tools, such as literacy assessments, teaching modules and textbooks, and the Merdeka Mengajar platform can be accessed via the website and Android application. The main aim of the Merdeka Curriculum is to develop students into Pancasila learners who are ready to face the future (Lestari et al., 2023, p. 86). Apart from that, this curriculum is applied at all levels of education, from PAUD to high school.

In Indonesia, the central government in 2013 began implementing a 12-year compulsory education program, which includes primary school (SD) for six years, junior high school (SMP) for three years, and senior high school (SMA) for three years.

Educational Curriculum in China

Like Indonesia, China is also implementing reforms to its education curriculum. Educational reform in China began in 1949, at the same time as the founding of the PRC under Mao's leadership. The first phase (1949-1952) was devoted to developing a national curriculum, instructional resources, and lesson plans. The PRC government issued educational materials in 1950 covering politics, science, moral education, and communist ideology for elementary school, middle school, and high school students. The Education System Law, passed a year later, determined the distribution of school levels. The levels are Initial Elementary School (two years), Advanced Elementary School (three years), Middle School (three years), and High School (three years) (Khalifardhi Nursyabana et al., 2022).

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Education focused on economic aspects in the second period from 1953 to 1957. The government updates the curriculum for elementary and middle schools. China's Ministry of Education issued a comprehensive curriculum in 1956. Mao said in 1957 that the goal of education should be communist-socialist philosophy. Due to the Cold War, there was a decline during the third era (1957-1963). Many students in elementary and middle schools are required to work in mines. After the curriculum revision 1958, primary to secondary education only took five years. Students are expected to understand the knowledge of Western countries in 10-12 years. Since 1949, China has reformed its education system to raise educational standards, produce skilled professionals, meet economic and development goals, and establish China as a global power. However, education suffered a setback under Mao's rule, with many students dropping out of school and losing the opportunity to receive an education (Nursyabana, 2022, p. 115).

After Mao Zedong died in 1976, Deng Xiaoping, China's revisionist leader, reflected on the educational needs of China's children. By establishing night schools, reducing illiteracy, and offering educational opportunities to all Chinese, Deng strove to raise academic standards. This initiative was effective, and after that, China expanded until it could compete with Western countries such as the United States and England. Because it emphasizes education as a foundation for building a solid nation, China is recognized as a super power country (Khalifardhi Nursyabana et al., 2022).

Furthermore, curriculum reform in the Jiang Zemin Era in 1993 was a significant era in the history of Chinese education. The education policy launched by Jiang Zemin has brought many positive changes to the country's education system. The responsibility of teaching students through the implementation of an enjoyable educational system that advances all aspects of humanity—in particular, cognitive development, character, and artistic development and skills—should be extended to education in China (WADIMAH, 2020, p. 2).

The last one is curriculum reform in the era of China's current President, Xi Jinping. Xi Jinping's thoughts are integrated into China's national curriculum. Students will study the Chinese President's political ideology from elementary school to university. The goal is to help "young people develop Marxist thought" and strengthen the role of the Chinese Communist Party in various sectors of society. Primary education at the elementary school level has three main focuses: cultivating socialism, the Chinese Communist Party, and love of the country. To help students create fundamental political judgments and ideas, middle schools will emphasize combining perceptual experience with knowledge, while universities will emphasize combining perceptual experience with studying knowledge. Emphasizes the development of theoretical thinking. This curriculum was only implemented in 2021 (Ilmie, 2021). Although the curriculum is constantly revised when leaders change, the changes made to the curriculum system are not only based on ideology or the leader's wishes. Still, they are based on the results of empirical research.

The education system in China begins at the age of six, with nine mandatory years of elementary school. Children can attend preschool education for several years before that. Compulsory education requires six years of primary school and three years of junior high school. Students take national exams to continue to high school after completing the lessons needed (Mareta Murdiyani, 2018, p. 2).

In China, the upper secondary education system is divided into three main categories:

1. A General High School aims to prepare students to continue to higher education.
2. Some specialist or technical high schools focus on providing specific skills and training in the technical field so that students are ready to work immediately after graduating. However, they also have the option to continue higher education.
3. Some Vocational or Professional High Schools offer specialized knowledge and training relevant to the needs of the world of work, preparing students to enter the job market after graduation.

All children in China will receive a quality primary education through the country's compulsory education system. After completing mandatory education, students can choose an educational path based on their interests and talents.

Students who complete general secondary education are prepared to continue to higher education. Students who complete vocational and technical secondary education are ready to work in the industrial sector. Exams at the end of the school semester determine a student's graduation from secondary education. The results of these exams and university entrance exams determine eligibility for further study. In China, there are many types of higher education institutions:

1. General and technical universities
2. Specialized universities (medicine, agriculture, foreign languages)
3. Teacher education vocational universities
4. Specialized academies

China has highly competitive entrance examinations for higher education. Universities, specialized institutes, and vocational universities all award bachelor's degrees. Further education is offered by vocational universities and specialized colleges, which also award degrees to their graduates. Some specialized institutions and universities award master's and doctoral degrees (Mareta Murdiyani, 2018, p. 3).

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Comparison of Curriculum Systems in Indonesia and China

The following are the results of a comparative study of the Indonesian and Chinese curricula based on four curriculum components, namely objectives, content/material, strategy and evaluation:

Goal Component

Indonesian national education aims to realize human potential spiritually, morally, intellectually and socially. This is by Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System. With education, it is hoped that we can create people who have faith and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, and are healthy, knowledgeable, intelligent, willing and able to work. They will also have personality, social and cultural abilities, and the ability to meet various demands. And restrain his desires (Cong Sujana, 2019, p. 31).

According to MPRS Decree No. XXVI/MPRS/1966 concerning Religion, Education and Culture, national education also functions to realize the actual Pancasila human being. UU no. 2 of 1989 confirms this, stating that national education aims to educate the life of the nation and develop the Indonesian people as a whole (Cong Sujana, 2019, p. 31).

Education in Indonesia tends to prioritize developing social and religious attitudes based on the first principle of Pancasila: Belief in One Almighty God. This shows that Indonesia upholds spirituality and recognizes the presence of God Almighty. Therefore, it cannot be denied that Indonesia is one of the most religious countries in the world.

China's national education aims to prepare students to develop holistically in four dimensions: moral, intellectual, physical, and aesthetic. This is done so they become socialist workers who are romantic, educated, cultured and have strong character and discipline in their future field. In recent years, China has focused on developing its education system to support its transition from an agricultural to an industrial civilization. Science and technology are increasingly emphasized. As a result, many Chinese people are successful in various fields, from education and industry to agriculture, all over the world. Chinese national education aims to create balanced, well-rounded individuals ready to contribute to the country's development (Mareta Murdiyani, 2018, p. 2).

Despite some differences, Indonesia's and China's national education goals are similar. Both countries aim to develop individuals of balance, quality and character who can contribute to national development.

Content/Material Components

The content/material components of the school curriculum describe what students learn. It includes all subjects taught and the material covered in each subject, all designed to help students achieve specific learning goals. (Aryanto et al., 2021, p. 1432) In the learning process, material is presented that supports achieving a goal. Based on Indonesia's independent curriculum, the Primary School Curriculum (SD) has several compulsory subjects, namely Natural and Social Sciences (IPAS), Religious Education and Character Education, and Education. Pancasila, Indonesian, Mathematics, Physical Education, Sports and Health, Arts and Culture, English and Local Content (Rahmadayanti & Hartoyo, 2022). At the junior high school level, there are several compulsory subjects, including informatics, religious education, Indonesian, Pancasila and citizenship education, arts and crafts, etc. At the high school level, the subjects taught by students in grade 10 are the same as those studied in junior high school: PPKN, English, natural sciences, social studies, mathematics, physical education and Indonesian. There are also elective subjects, including informatics, arts and crafts, and local content. Meanwhile, the topics are separated into five categories for grades 11 and 12: the general subject group of Social Sciences, Mathematics and Natural Sciences, culture, language, and the vocational and crafts group (Akbar, n.d.).

Meanwhile, the education system in China has a different structure at each level of education. At the elementary school (SD) level, students must take ten compulsory subjects. These subjects include Morals, Mathematics, and Chinese. The number of mandatory subjects at the Junior High School (SMP) level increases to 13. Morals, Mandarin, Foreign Languages and Politics are some subjects that must be studied at this level (Mareta Murdiyani, 2018, p. 4).

Unlike elementary and middle schools, high schools (SMA) in China do not have compulsory subjects. This is because high schools in China implement a system that adapts subjects to students' wishes, the social needs of society, and the conditions of local institutions. With this system, students can choose the subjects they want to study according to their interests and talents. Apart from that, schools can also offer elective subjects that suit the social needs of the community and the conditions of local institutions. China's flexible education system can help students develop their potential to the maximum and prepare them to face a future full of challenges (Mareta Murdiyani, 2018, p. 4).

Strategy Components

Learning strategies are an essential element to study in the curriculum, both on a macro and micro scale. This strategy refers to a method or system for delivering curriculum content (delivery system) that is designed to achieve educational goals that have been formulated. More than just procedures or processes, educational strategies include approaches, methods, models and tactics teachers apply in presenting material—/curriculum content. Strategy is like a strategy or tactic teachers apply to carry out the curriculum structurally and in a planned manner. Therefore, so that the curriculum components can be arranged in an integrated manner and achieve goals, there must be a connection between these components and a structure to support achieving these goals. In other

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words, educational strategy is the key to bridging the curriculum and achieving academic goals. Appropriate and efficient strategies will help teachers help students achieve maximum learning outcomes (Maryati, 2020, p. 60).

In Indonesia, teachers usually use several learning strategies, including the following: First, Collaborative Learning Strategy: In the independent curriculum, students are encouraged to collaborate in small groups when working on assignments. This strategy allows students to interact and exchange ideas to achieve learning goals. Collaboration also helps students to deepen their understanding of concepts. By exchanging ideas and perspectives, students can view learning material from various points of view and build richer knowledge (Hasanah & Haryadi, 2022, pp. 271–272). Second, Project-Based Education Strategy: students are encouraged to participate in an actual project in the independent curriculum. This strategy allows them to practice the knowledge and skills they have learned in a relevant and meaningful context. More than just doing assignments, projects provide opportunities for students to experience a complete learning experience. They know how to work in teams with friends and encounter various challenges that hone their creativity and critical thinking (Novitasary, 2023). Third, Inquiry-Based Education Strategy: Students are encouraged to explore and create knowledge independently in the independent curriculum. This strategy is different from traditional education, which has a passive nature, where the teacher is the only data source. An inquiry-based education strategy allows students to ask questions, conduct investigations, and create answers. Overall, the inquiry-based educational strategies in the Merdeka Curriculum help students become active, independent learners and able to think critically. Teachers use not only these three educational strategies but also many more educational strategies in education. These three strategies are just examples of the many types of strategies in education..

Meanwhile, the strategy used by China has several interesting characteristics. Among them:

1. Warm up before learning: Students are invited to warm up first before learning begins. This activity aims to protect physical health and increase the enthusiasm of students.
2. School Picket Activities: In China, picketing and school cleaning are done together. All students gather in the school area to sweep, mop and clean the toilets. The goal is to increase student collaboration and discipline.
3. Longer study time: The learning system in China allows longer study hours than in Indonesia. Students can study from 8 am to 4 pm. Even high school students often continue studying until 8 pm. The high level of competence encourages many parents to choose private educational institutions.
4. Independent Study: Unlike Indonesia, students in China have independent study sessions. After learning with the help of a teacher, they continue studying independently. Some schools even require students to take independent study sessions at school.
5. Nap Culture: In some Chinese schools, there is a nap time after lunch. This helps students feel refreshed and ready to face the rest of the class day.
6. Daily Ranking: Students in China are often ranked based on their academic performance daily. This encourages a spirit of learning and competition among students (Savitri Fatimaningrum, n.d.).

China's education system focuses on strong character, discipline, and achievement. The Chinese government also pays special attention to the education sector, creating a competitive and quality learning environment.

Evaluation Component

Evaluation is a fundamental pillar in the formal education system. For teachers, evaluation is like a mirror that reflects the effectiveness of their performance. Information obtained from evaluations helps teachers understand the strengths and weaknesses in the learning process to continue improving the quality of their teaching. On the other hand, evaluation is also a valuable source of information for curriculum developers. The evaluation results provide an overview of the effectiveness of the current curriculum, identify weaknesses and gaps, and pave the way for efforts to improve and develop a more adaptive and optimal curriculum. Even though it is often identified as a final activity, evaluation plays a broader role (Sukmawati, 2021, p. 68).

In the current independent curriculum, the Minister of Education in terms of evaluation, makes policies:

1. The National Examination (UN) was removed. This was done because the National Examination rules were deemed inappropriate. This rule has students' cognitive orientation, which makes them focus only on memorizing the material rather than understanding it. Even before the Independent Curriculum was launched, the National Examination was abolished in 2021. The implementation of the Independent Curriculum brought changes to the final assessment system. The National Examination (UN), previously held at the end of the education level, was replaced with the Minimum Competency Assessment (AKM) and Character Survey. The Minimum Competency Assessment (AKM) and Character Survey have replaced the National Examination (UN) previously carried out at the end of the education program. AKM was introduced in grades IV, VIII, and XI to provide schools with input on improving the learning process before students graduate. This is different from the National Examination, which is only held after the end of the education program. This innovation is expected to provide more comprehensive data about students' abilities and character, thereby helping schools improve the quality of learning and character education (Marisa, 2024, p. 72).

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2. The National School-Based Examination (USBN) is replaced by an assessment carried out by portfolio-based schools. Assessment or evaluation in the independent curriculum is a series of activities to measure students' learning abilities. There are two categories of assessments used in the Merdeka Curriculum (Nur Budiono & Hatip, 2023):

a) **Formative Assessment:**

Purpose: Formative assessment aims to reflect the learning process and function as an evaluation tool during learning.

Benefits: Teachers can master learning methods that are very efficient for each student. This assessment provides a more detailed picture of how well students absorb learning material. This assessment shows the development of individual student learning outcomes based on their learning methods. Teachers can determine whether the learning methods implemented are adequate or need improvement. Comprehensive assessments can motivate students to study harder or maintain their achievements. These assessments help teachers identify the potential and interests of each student.

b) **Summative Assessment:**

Objective: Summative assessments are carried out at the end of the learning process, aiming to assess student achievement and overall learning outcomes.

Benefits: Provides an overview of student learning outcomes as a whole, Provides information that can be used to evaluate learning programs, Provides relevant data for decision-making regarding student graduation and Facilitates the preparation of subsequent learning plans.

Meanwhile, in China, the evaluation system at the elementary school level does not apply national exams for graduation requirements. To continue to junior high school, elementary school students must meet graduation standards and learning success. The report card grades during elementary school studies are used as a reference, with a minimum score of 80 for the main subjects Mandarin, Mathematics and English. On the other hand, for different subjects such as sports, social studies, science, music and computers, the passing standard is 70 (Murdiyani, 2018, p. h. 7).

Different from the elementary school level, at the secondary school level (Junior High School and Senior High School) national exams or graduation exams known as the Huikao and Gaoko exams are implemented. The huikao exam is a school exam different from the national exam. This exam covers subjects not included in the national exam; at the junior high school level, the subjects tested are Sports, Social Sciences (Geography, History, Political Science), Natural Sciences (Chemistry, Physics and Biology), Music and Computers. The tests for the high school level are for Computer, Arts and Sports subjects. The Huikao Exam aims to assess students' understanding of the subject and assist schools in determining student graduation. Meanwhile, the Gaokao Examination is a national examination organized by the Chinese Ministry of Education. Mandarin, English, and Mathematics are the focus of this exam. The results of the Gaokao Examination greatly determine a student's chances of entering the university they want (Mareta Murdiyani, 2018, p. 7).

The examination system in China continues to develop and undergo reforms to improve the quality of education. Although the main focus is still on measuring rote knowledge and ability to solve problems, efforts are being made to develop more holistic and comprehensive assessment methods. Overall, China's examination system is designed to encourage students to work hard and achieve high academic achievements. This system has several advantages and disadvantages and is continually being improved to improve the quality of education in China.

CONCLUSION

Based on a comparative study of the education curriculum systems in Indonesia and China, it can be concluded that:

1. Both Indonesia and China have experienced changes or reforms in curriculum development, which aims to follow the needs of society.
2. Indonesia has a 12-year compulsory education program, and China has a mandatory education program with nine years of study.
3. Even though they have differences, national education goals in Indonesia and China also have similarities. The aim is to develop balanced, qualified, and characterful individuals who can contribute to national development.
4. The content/material taught in Indonesia and China at The elementary-middle school levels have similarities, namely that the government has determined both. In contrast, at the high school level in China, there are no compulsory subjects; in Indonesia, the subjects at the high school level are still determined by the government.
5. The strategies used in Indonesia include group-based learning strategies, projects and inquiry. In contrast, the strategy used by China has several interesting characteristics that differentiate it from education systems in other countries, including implementing naps during learning.
6. in Indonesia, the national exam is no longer implemented, while in China, the national exam is still implemented, known as the gaokao exam.

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